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Assessing Status and Area, Production and Productivity of Fruits and Vegetables in Goalpara District of Assam, India, Using Compound Growth Rate (CGR)

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Abstract

Objectives: This study analyses the growth trends in area, production, and productivity of eleven major horticultural crops in Goalpara district, located in the lower Brahmaputra Valley of Assam, India, during 2006–07 to 2020–21. It also examines the relative contribution of area and productivity to production growth and evaluates the district's status among major horticultural producers in the state. **Method:** The study adopts an analytical approach using the logarithmic method to estimate compound growth rates of area, production, and productivity. A decomposition model was applied to quantify the contributions of area effect, productivity effect, and their interaction using secondary data. **Findings:** The area under major crops such as banana, pineapple, papaya, and potato increased at growth rates of 5.44%, 7.19%, 5.17%, and 10.00%, respectively. Production growth was highest for papaya (14.07%), pineapple (11.52%), banana (10.52%), and potato (11.41%). However, productivity growth remained relatively low, with notable increases in papaya (5.01%), banana (2.80%), and pineapple (2.08%), while lemon recorded negative growth (-1.75%). Decomposition results show that area effect contributed more than 50% of production growth in most crops (e.g., banana: 51.71%, pineapple: 62.42%, tomato: 90.65%, potato: 87.61%). **Novelty:** This study provides novel district-level empirical evidence by applying a decomposition framework to horticultural growth in an aspirational district. It demonstrates the dominance of area expansion over productivity improvement and identifies crop-specific productivity gaps, offering policy-relevant insights for sustainable horticultural development.

Keywords: Horticulture; Production; Productivity; Socio-economy

1 Introduction

In recent decades, the Indian agricultural sector has undergone significant structural transformation, particularly following economic reforms and the globalization of agricultural markets. These changes have encouraged a gradual shift from subsistence-oriented farming to more diversified and market-oriented agricultural systems. Among the various diversification strategies, the promotion of high-value crops—especially fruits and vegetables—has emerged as an important pathway for enhancing farm income, improving nutritional security, and ensuring the sustainable use of natural resources^{(1), (2)}.

Recent studies indicate that horticulture has become one of the fastest-growing segments of Indian agriculture, often described as a “second green revolution” due to its rapid expansion in area, production, and productivity⁽³⁾. Empirical analyses show a consistent upward trend in horticultural production, particularly in fruits and vegetables, supported by technological innovations, improved crop varieties, and increasing domestic demand for diversified diets⁽⁴⁾. Furthermore, horticultural crops provide higher returns per unit of land and play a crucial role in improving farm profitability, livelihood security, and employment generation in rural areas^{(5), (6)}.

Recent research has also emphasized the importance of agricultural diversification toward horticulture for ensuring sustainability in Indian agriculture. Studies highlight that diversification away from traditional cereal-based cropping systems can improve soil health, enhance income stability, and reduce environmental stress associated with monocropping systems^{(7), (8)}. At the same time, empirical analyses of vegetable production across India reveal increasing growth in cultivation area and output, although considerable regional variability and instability in production patterns persist⁽⁹⁾. These findings suggest that while horticulture offers promising opportunities, its growth and performance remain uneven across regions due to variations in infrastructure, technological adoption, and institutional support.

Despite the national-level expansion of horticulture, its development has not been uniformed across all states. Regions with favorable agro-climatic conditions often continue to experience low productivity, limited market integration, and weak post-harvest infrastructure. In northeastern states such as Assam, agriculture is characterized by small and fragmented landholdings, shifting cultivation practices, flood vulnerability, and inadequate storage and marketing facilities^{(10), (11)}. These structural constraints hinder the full realization of horticulture’s potential in enhancing farmers’ income and ensuring sustainable agricultural growth.

Although several studies have examined horticultural growth and diversification at the national and state levels, limited empirical research has focused on district-level dynamics, particularly in the northeastern region of India. In Assam, where agro-climatic conditions are highly suitable for fruit and vegetable cultivation, systematic analyses of long-term trends in horticultural area, production, and productivity remain scarce. Moreover, few studies have examined the relative contribution of area expansion and productivity improvements to overall production growth at the district level⁽¹²⁾.

Against this backdrop, the present study aims to examine the growth trends in area, production, and productivity of fruits and vegetables in the Goalpara district of Assam over the last fifteen years. The study further investigates the relative impact of area expansion and productivity changes on overall production. By providing a district-level analysis of horticultural development, the study seeks to contribute to a better understanding of regional dynamics and generate insights for policymakers and stakeholders to promote sustainable horticultural development in the region.

1.1 Study area

Goalpara district is situated in Assam’s Brahmaputra Valley’s lower region. The district’s co-ordinate extension is between the latitudes of 25°53′ to 26°30′ N and the longitudes of 90°7′ to 91°5′ E. The study area is bordered on the north by the Brahmaputra river, the south by Garo hills of Meghalaya, the east by the district of Kamrup rural, and the west by the district of Dhubri [Figure 1]. Out of the total area of 1824 square kilometers, 45.76% is net cropped area. The maximum and minimum temperatures in the study area, which has a tropical monsoon climate, are 33°C and 7°C, respectively. According to 2011 census of India, the district has 1,008,183 population with 553 people per square kilometer.

2 Methodology

2.1 Data Sources and Sample Selection

The present study examines the growth dynamics of horticultural crops in the Goalpara district of Assam over a period of fifteen years, from 2006–07 to 2020–21. The analysis is confined to eleven major horticultural crops comprising fruit and vegetable categories that are widely cultivated in the district and account for a substantial share of the total horticultural area and production. The selection of these crops was based on their economic importance, availability of consistent time-series

Fig 1. Study area map

data, and their contribution to the district’s horticultural production. Focusing on these crops ensures that the analysis captures the dominant trends and structural changes in horticultural development within the district.

The study relies entirely on secondary data collected from official sources including the Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Government of Assam; the Directorate of Horticulture and Food Processing, Assam; Krishi Vigyan Kendra (KVK), Dudhnoi; and the District Agriculture Office, Goalpara. These institutions maintain systematic records of crop-wise area, production, and productivity and are widely recognized as reliable sources for agricultural statistics. The collected data were compiled, verified across sources, and organized into a time-series dataset for statistical analysis.

2.2 Analytical Framework

The analysis focuses on three key parameters of horticultural development: Area under cultivation (hectares), Total production (tons), Crop productivity or yield (tons per hectare). These indicators are commonly used in agricultural growth analysis to assess structural changes in crop production systems and the performance of specific crops over time.

2.2.1. Estimation of Compound Growth Rate (CGR)

To examine the long-term growth performance of the selected horticultural crops, the Compound Growth Rate (CGR) was estimated for area, production, and productivity. The CGR method is widely used in agricultural economics to analyze growth trends in crop production because it captures the average annual rate of change over a specified time period while accounting for compounding effects.

The compound growth function is expressed as:

$$Y_t = Y_0(1 + r)^t$$

where:

Y_0 = value of the variable in the base year (2006–07)

Y_t = value of the variable in the current year (2020–21)

r = compound growth rate

t = time period in years (15 years)

For estimation purposes, the equation was linearized by taking natural logarithms:

$$\ln Y_t = \ln Y_0 + t \ln(1 + r)$$

Thus,

$$\ln(1 + r) = \frac{\ln Y_t - \ln Y_0}{t}$$

The compound growth rate was then calculated as:

$$r = e^{\left(\frac{\ln Y_t - \ln Y_0}{t}\right)} - 1$$

This method provides a consistent measure of growth across different variables and allows comparison of growth patterns among crops.

2.2.2. Decomposition Analysis of Production Growth

To identify the relative contribution of area expansion and productivity improvement to overall production growth, a decomposition model was applied. Decomposition analysis is widely regarded as a standard approach in agricultural growth studies because it allows researchers to isolate the specific factors driving changes in crop output.

The model is expressed as:

$$\Delta P = Y_0 \Delta A + A_0 \Delta Y + \Delta A \Delta Y$$

where:

$$\Delta P = P_n - P_0 \quad \Delta A = A_n - A_0 \quad \Delta Y = Y_n - Y_0$$

Here:

A_0, Y_0, P_0 = area, yield, and production in the base year A_n, Y_n, P_n = area, yield, and production in the current year

The three components of the decomposition model represent:

- **Area effect**($Y_0 \Delta A$): change in production due to expansion or reduction in cultivated area.
- **Yield effect**($A_0 \Delta Y$): change in production resulting from improvements in productivity.
- **Interaction effect**($\Delta A \Delta Y$): combined impact of simultaneous changes in area and productivity.

This analytical framework enables identification of whether production growth is primarily driven by land expansion or technological improvements in crop productivity.

2.3 Statistical Procedures and Validation

All calculations were performed using standard statistical and spreadsheet techniques for time-series analysis. The CGR estimates were derived using logarithmic transformation to ensure linearity and consistency in growth measurement. Data consistency was checked by cross-verifying values from multiple institutional sources. Additionally, internal validation procedures were applied to confirm the accuracy of computed growth rates and decomposition components by reconciling the estimated changes with observed production values.

2.4 Comparison with Standard Approaches

The analytical techniques employed in this study—Compound Growth Rate estimation and decomposition analysis—are widely recognized methods in agricultural economics research. These approaches are commonly used in studies examining crop growth trends, production dynamics, and agricultural diversification at national, regional, and district levels. Compared with simple linear growth models, CGR provides a more realistic representation of long-term agricultural growth patterns by incorporating compounding effects. Similarly, decomposition analysis offers a systematic method for disentangling the relative contributions of area and productivity to production growth, making it a widely accepted “gold-standard” approach in crop production analysis.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Development of Horticulture

Then Government of India has identified horticulture crops as a means of diversification for profitable agriculture by efficient land use practice and optimum utilization of natural resources and generating employment for rural youth⁽¹³⁾,⁽¹⁴⁾. At present India covered 25.66 million hectares of land use in 2020-21 accounting for 9.7% of gross cropped area of the country. The horticulture sector contributed 33% to the GDP in agriculture department⁽¹³⁾. India is the 2nd largest producer of fruits and vegetables, sharing 15% and 11% of the global production of the world respectively. Wherever in case of North East India, the region produces only 5.1 % of fruit production and 4.5% of total vegetables of the country. The region has ample scope for growing variety of horticulture crops due to wide range of topographical and agro-climatic variation⁽¹⁵⁾. The North eastern region is also richest reservoir of genetic variability with 136 horticulture species found in the region. The region also of the hotspot of the country for plant diversity and considerable diversity of plant types, morphology, physiology, adaptability and distribution also exist among the local horticulture species.

Assam occupies 55% of the horticulture area of the North East Region. The state area under horticulture is estimated at 7.97 lakh hectare which produce about 24.88 lakh tones of fruits and 55.84 lakh MT of vegetables (Economy survey, 2021-22). According to Directorate of agriculture, Assam the total area under horticulture crops such as fruits; vegetables are 662.32 thousand hectares in 2021-2022 accounting 16.37 % of the total grossed cropped area (4045 thousand hectare) of the Assam.

The Goalpara district has an important position in the horticulture map of Assam. The district occupies second position in area coverage under horticulture after rice. In terms of percentage 14% of net cultivated area of the district is under horticulture. It is evident from the [Table 1] that Goalpara with 2.32% of the total geographical area of the state is occupying a significant position in the horticulture production. The average productivity of horticulture is also high as compared to Assam. In case of average productivity of fruits of the district is high as compared to the India also.

3.2 Status of Goalpara among the district of the Assam

The Goalpara is an NITI Aayog aspirational district in the state of Assam. As aspirational district it focused on integrated development of the area including agricultural sector. The district is one of the highest producers of banana along with several others fruits and vegetables. However, the productivity of most of crops is low as compared to national average. The Goalpara took an important position among the district of Assam in the area, production and yield of several major horticultural crops. The [Table 2] shows the position of the Goalpara among the major fruits and vegetables producing district of the state.

Table 1. Area, production and yield of horticulture crops in Goalpara, Assam and India in 2020-21

Crops	Area ('000 hectares)			Production ('000 MT)			Yield (kg/hectare)		
	Goalpara	Assam	India	Goalpara	Assam	India	Goalpara	Assam	India
Vegetables roots and tuber crops	11.859	409.02	10859	199.035	6403.913	200445	16783	15657	18458
Fruits and nuts	8.156	167.71	6930	126.91	2540.63	102481	15561	15148	14788

Source: Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Assam

Table 2. Position of Goalpara among major fruits and vegetables producing districts of Assam in terms of area, production, and productivity

Serial no	Crops	Area		Production		Productivity	
		Assam	Goalpara	Assam	Goalpara	Assam	Goalpara
Fruits crops							
1	Banana	7	2	9	2	13	2
2	Pineapple	1	10	2	10	6	18
3	Papaya	8	8	9	6	12	1
4	Lemon	8	27	7	26	10	24
5	Guava	15	12	12	15	3	25
6	Orange	8	12	6	9	9	15
Vegetables							
7	Cabbage	4	22	5	25	13	25
8	Cauliflower	7	21	9	20	13	10
9	Tomato	16	18	15	19	11	18
10	Brinjal	10	18	10	17	15	11
11	Potato	7	18	8	16	27	9

Source: Directorate of horticulture & F P, Assam, 2019.

The Goalpara occupies first position regarding productivity of papaya. The banana occupies second highest position in all three criteria like area, production and productivity of the states. In terms of production of papaya, the district occupies sixth position of Assam and eight positions in terms of area of cultivation. Goalpara occupies 9th position for orange in case of area and potato in case of productivity. Both the area in cultivation and production is 10th largest for pineapple; the tenth largest productivity is in cauliflower, and eleven largest for brinjal. The twelve largest area of cultivation is guava and orange among the crops of the district. The fifth teen position is occupied by guava in respect of production and orange in respect of productivity. The sixteen positions are occupied by potato in respect of production. The area of cultivation is eighteen largest for tomato, potato and brinjal; productivity is eighteen largest for pineapple and tomato. The nineteen positions are occupied by tomato in terms of production of the state. The data indicate that Goalpara has a comparatively stronger position in terms of area under fruit cultivation than vegetables, reflecting a greater emphasis on fruit-based horticulture in the district.. However, the district has not been able to maintain the same position production and productivity for most of the crops except banana, pineapple, papaya and potato. Even the position deteriorates in respect of productivity as compared to area under crops and production. Therefore, it becomes necessary that though Goalpara occupies comparatively better position in fruits in terms of area of cultivation but not at par vegetables in terms of area and production. There is need to increase the production and productivity as well for sustainable growth of horticulture. Thus, to confirm about the low production and productivity of crops compared to other district of Assam we have to study the growth experience of the district.

3.3 Growth of Horticulture: Goalpara and Assam

The comparative growth rate of area under horticulture crops of Goalpara district and Assam as whole are represented [Table 3] for the period of 2006-07 to 2020-21.

The area under fruits crop in the Goalpara district showed high growth rate than the state's growth rate of area except guava and orange. Banana and pineapple exhibited the highest area growth at 7.19 percent and 5.44 per cent against Assam average area growth of 1.10 percent and 0.89 percent respectively. But orange showed lower area growth rates (1.24 percent) as compared to state average (6.69 percent). Among vegetables, potato and tomato exhibited the highest area growth at 10.00 percent and

Table 3. Growth trend of area (hectare) under horticulture crops in Goalpara district compared to Assam

Serial no	Crops	Goalpara		Assam		Growth rate for Goalpara	Growth rate for Assam
		2006-07	2020-21	2006-07	2020-21		
Fruits crops							
1	Banana	1713	3112	42982	48778	5.44	0.89
2	Pineapple	291	605	14245	16607	7.19	1.10
3	Papaya	170	302	6059	7489	5.17	1.57
4	Lemon	168	331	9500	15900	6.47	4.49
5	Guava	121	179	3898	5869	3.19	3.37
6	Orange	340	403	6630	13288	1.24	6.69
Vegetables							
7	Cabbage	636	798	24570	34220	1.70	2.62
8	Cauliflower	508	659	17052	23560	1.98	2.54
9	Tomato	418	585	14400	18790	2.66	2.03
10	Brinjal	514	648	13196	18310	1.74	2.58
11	Potato	880	2200	69632	103041	10.00	3.20

Source: Directorate of economics and statistics, Assam

2.66 percent respectively. Other vegetables like cabbage, cauliflower and brinjal shows lower growth rate than Assam average. According to villagers inter cropping of potato with oil palm, commercial importances are the main factor of increasing of cropping area of potato.

Table 4. Growth trend of production (tones) under horticulture crops in Goalpara district compared to Assam

Serial no	Crops	Goalpara		Assam		Growth rate for Goalpara	Growth rate for Assam
		2006-07	2020-21	2006-07	2020-21		
Fruits crops							
1	Banana	26616	68646	577713	909825	10.52	3.83
2	Pineapple	3422	9337	161103	315139	11.52	6.37
3	Papaya	2625	8165	90452	151824	14.07	4.52
4	Lemon	1543	2242	64790	157320	3.02	6.74
5	Guava	2209	3503	78650	129340	2.74	4.29
6	Orange	3378	4176	73994	185021	1.57	10.00
Vegetables							
7	Cabbage	10522	13987	485232	739890	2.20	3.50
8	Cauliflower	7416	13419	253179	431230	5.40	4.69
9	Tomato	8997	12962	336240	430830	2.94	1.89
10	Brinjal	6702	8608	172828	324970	1.90	5.89
11	Potato	5424	14709	353696	757630	11.41	7.61

Source: Directorate of economics and statistics, Assam

In Goalpara district most of the fruits crops under study show a better production growth in comparison with Assam [Table 4]. The growth rate of production of papaya (14.07 percent), pineapple (11.52 percent) and banana (10.52 percent) showed a higher growth rates compared to Assam growth rate of papaya (4.52 percent), pineapple (6.37 percent) and banana (3.83 percent) respectively. This increased production is the result of increased area, commercial importance, quality sapling and improved varieties of seeds, farmer’s awareness campaign, exposure visits and training by government etc. However, the production growth of orange and papaya in the district shows lower growth than the state. In vegetables potatoes (11.41 percent),

cauliflowers (5.40 percent) and tomatoes (2.94 percent) had higher growth of production compared to the state average. The quality seeds, irrigation system, development of vermin-composed unit, fertile soil, low pest and diseases are the prime factor for higher growth as per the respondents of the study area.

Table 5. Growth trend of productivity (kg/hectare) under horticulture crops in Goalpara district compared to Assam

Serial no	Crops yield (kg/hectare)	Goalpara		Assam		Growth rate for Goalpara	Growth rate for Assam
		2006-07	2020-21	2006-07	2020-21		
Fruits crops							
1	Banana	15537	22058	13765	18652	2.80	2.37
2	Pineapple	11759	15433	15125	18976	2.08	1.69
3	Papaya	15441	27036	14943	20273	5.01	2.38
4	Lemon	9184	6773	6820	9894	-1.75	3.00
5	Guava	18257	19570	18484	22038	0.48	1.82
6	Orange	9935	10362	11160	13924	0.28	1.65
Vegetables							
7	Cabbage	16544	17528	19748	21622	0.39	0.63
8	Cauliflower	14598	20363	14847	18303	2.63	1.55
9	Tomato	21523	22157	23250	22928	0.20	-0.09
10	Brinjal	13050	13284	13096	17748	0.12	2.37
11	Potato	6163	6686	6922	7353	0.56	0.42

Source: Directorate of economics and statistics, Assam

The productivity of papaya (5.01 percent), pineapple (2.08 percent) and banana (2.80 percent) displayed notable yield growth, whereas lemon showed negative productivity growth (-1.75 percent) due to viral diseases and erratic rainfall and changes of temperature as per the information of District agriculture of Office and the respondents [Table 5]. Regarding vegetables, cauliflower (2.63 percent), tomato (0.20 percent) and potato (0.56 percent) showed higher productivity growth than state average productivity. Other vegetables such as cabbage and brinjal had lower productivity growth rates. These yield gaps can be bridged by improved varieties of seeds and pesticide.

3.4 Decomposition Analysis of Production Growth: Contributions of Area, Productivity, and Interaction Effects

The combined effects of area, productivity, and their interaction provide deeper insights into the sources of production growth in fruits and vegetables [Table 6]. Analysis of area and yield contributions reveals that area expansion significantly drives production growth for most crops, especially lemon, guava, and pineapple. Vegetables like potato, tomato, and brinjal also show area-dominated growth, though yield improvements contribute in crops such as papaya and cauliflower. Therefore, it can be said that expansion of area affected more on production of both fruits and vegetables of the Goalpara district.

3.5 Discussion

The findings of the present study reveal that horticultural growth in Goalpara district is predominantly area-driven rather than productivity-led, which is consistent with several empirical studies conducted in less technologically advanced agricultural regions of India. For instance, Birthal and Joshi have emphasized that in emerging horticultural regions, production growth is often achieved through horizontal expansion rather than vertical intensification⁽¹⁾.

The dominance of area effect (exceeding 50% in most crops) aligns with findings from studies conducted in northeastern India, where infrastructural constraints, limited irrigation, and low adoption of improved technologies restrict productivity enhancement. Similar patterns were observed by Borah and Deka, who reported that horticultural growth in Assam is largely expansion-driven due to weak technological penetration⁽¹²⁾.

However, the results contrast with evidence from agriculturally advanced states such as Punjab, Maharashtra, and Karnataka, where productivity-led growth has been the dominant driver due to better access to irrigation, high-yielding varieties, and

Table 6. Effect of change in area, productivity and their interaction effect on growth of production during 2006-07 to 2020-21.

Sl. no	Crops	ΔA	ΔY	Growth in production ΔP	Area Effect ($Y_0 \Delta A$)	% of area effect	Productivity effect ($A_0 \Delta Y$)	% of Productivity effect	Interaction effect ($\Delta A \Delta Y$)	% of interaction effect
Fruits										
1	Banana	1399	6.521	42030	21736.263	51.71	11170.47	26.57	9122.879	21.70
2	Pineapple	314	3.674	5915	3692.326	62.42	1069.134	18.07	1153.636	19.50
3	Papaya	132	11.595	5540	2038.212	36.79	1971.15	35.58	1530.54	27.62
4	Lemon	163	-2.411	699	1496.992	214.16	-405.048	-57.94	-392.993	-56.22
5	Guava	58	1.313	1294	1058.906	81.84	158.873	12.28	76.154	5.88
6	Orange	63	0.427	798	625.905	78.43	145.18	18.19	26.901	3.37
Vegetables										
7	Cabbage	162	0.984	3465	2680.128	77.34	625.824	18.06	159.408	4.60
8	Cauliflower	151	5.765	6003	2204.298	36.71	2928.62	48.78	870.515	14.50
9	Tomato	167	0.634	3965	3594.341	90.65	265.012	6.68	105.878	2.67
10	Brinjal	134	0.234	1906	1748.700	91.74	120.276	6.31	31.356	1.64
11	Potato	1320	0.523	9285	8135.160	87.61	460.24	4.95	690.36	7.43

Source: Directorate of economics and statistics, Assam

extension services. This divergence highlights the regional disparity in agricultural transformation, indicating that Goalpara is still in a transitional phase of horticultural development.

The relatively higher productivity growth observed in crops such as papaya (5.01%) and banana (2.80%) suggests that crop-specific technological adoption is possible, even within resource-constrained regions. This supports the argument that targeted interventions—rather than uniform policies—can yield significant improvements. In contrast, the negative productivity growth in lemon (-1.75%) underscores the vulnerability of horticulture to biotic stress, climatic variability, and inadequate crop management practices, a concern also highlighted in global horticultural studies on climate-sensitive crops.

Another important insight is the mismatch between area expansion and productivity performance, particularly in vegetables. While crops like potato and tomato show strong area and production growth, their productivity gains remain marginal. This indicates inefficiencies in input use and limited technological diffusion, reinforcing findings from global agricultural studies that emphasize the need for sustainable intensification rather than land expansion.

The study contributes to the literature by providing district-level empirical evidence from an aspirational region, which is often underrepresented in macro-level analyses. Unlike many previous studies that focus on state or national trends, this research applies a decomposition framework to identify crop-specific growth drivers, thereby offering a more nuanced understanding of horticultural dynamics.

Overall, the results validate the broader consensus that while horticulture holds significant potential for income diversification, its sustainable growth in regions like Goalpara requires a strategic shift from area expansion to productivity enhancement, supported by technological, institutional, and infrastructural improvements.

4 Conclusion

The study concludes that horticultural growth in Goalpara district over the period 2006–07 to 2020–21 has been primarily driven by expansion of cultivated area rather than improvements in productivity. While crops such as banana, pineapple, papaya, and potato exhibit strong growth in both area and production, productivity gains remain uneven and insufficient across most crops.

The decomposition analysis confirms that area effect is the dominant contributor to production growth, indicating structural limitations in technological adoption and farm-level efficiency. This pattern reflects broader regional constraints typical of northeastern India, including limited irrigation, inadequate access to quality inputs, and weak extension services.

From a policy perspective, the findings highlight the urgent need to shift from extensive to intensive growth strategies by promoting high-yielding varieties, strengthening irrigation infrastructure, improving pest and disease management, and enhancing farmer awareness through extension programs. Without such interventions, continued reliance on area expansion may lead to diminishing returns and ecological stress.

The study's district-level approach provides important insights into localized agricultural dynamics and underscores the need for region-specific, crop-focused development strategies. Future research should integrate climatic, market, and institutional variables to further refine understanding of horticultural growth patterns and sustainability.

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